

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock and Wilson, 1972. Settlement Patterns and Community Organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-259.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fn17-001>
- Source 1 Description: Wilson, Monica Hunter. 1951. "Good Company: A Study Of Nyakyusa Age-Villages." London: Oxford University Press for the International African Institute.
- Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fn17-002>
- Source 2 Description: Wilson, Monica Hunter. 1957. "Rituals Of Kinship Among The Nyakyusa." London: Oxford University Press for the International African Institute.
- Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fn17-009>.
- Source 3 Description: Wilson, Monica Hunter. 1959. "Communal Rituals Of The Nyakyusa." London, New York, Toronto: Published for the International Institute by the Oxford University Press.
- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fn17-006>.
- Source 1 Description: Wilson, Godfrey. 1939. "Constitution Of Ngonde." Rhodes-Livingstone Papers. Livingstone, Northern Rhodesia: The Rhodes-Livingstone Institute.
- Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fn17-000>.
- Source 2 Description: Kenny, Michael G. 2011. "Culture Summary: Nyakyusa And Ngonde." New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "German missionaries of the Berlin and Moravian missions arrived in 1891, and established themselves at a number of stations in Nyakyusa country" (Wilson, 1951:11).

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Relations between the Nyakyusa and Europeans was accommodating. "After these journeys of discovery [referring to European explorers ca. 1875], mission work and trade

developed quickly. The African Lakes Corporation, a company formed to develop legitimate trade in Central Africa as a means of combating the [Arab] slave trade, established a station at Karonga; and a road was surveyed from Karonga through to Lake Tanganyika" (Wilson, 1951:10).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Violence between Nyakyusa villages was not an uncommon phenomenon. For example: "A man was a member both of a village and of a lineage and both groups were responsible for his behaviour. An adulterer or cattle-thief was speared by the injured party and his kinsmen, if they could catch him. If they could not, they might attack any member of his age-village. This commonly led to war between the villages" (Wilson, 1957:2).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: "With the Sangu to the north the Nyakyusa were continually at war; they did not trade or pray with them" (Wilson, 1959:97).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because Nyakyusa beliefs are interwoven with society and culture at large, it is not an organized, official religion that would have a process for assigning affiliation.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The religious and political aspects of Nyakyusa are coterminous. As such, chiefs do not officially declare support for the religion. Political leadership is not synonymous with religious leadership, but Nyakyusa chiefs are believed to have superior supernatural powers. "The great medicines of chieftainship are ifingila and their function is to create amanga, i.e. spiritual power, and ubusisya, i.e. dignity, majesty, in order to make the chief fearful 'so that men obey him'. The medicines are comparable to robes of office for they are designed to give their user assurance and fill the commonality with awe. The Nyakyusa also think that chiefs and headmen should be 'heavy' with 'pythons in their bellies' which give them the power to see and fight witches. Without such a 'python' a chief or village headman cannot fulfil his duty of 'watching over the country by day and by night' and if a man is not born with one he may develop it through the proper use of medicines" (Wilson, 1959:57).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 195000

Notes: "In 1931 the Nyakyusa population was approximately 195,000..." (eHRAF World Culture, FN17 Culture Summary).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 84

Notes: The majority of the Nyakyusa subscribe to the same set of native beliefs, aside from those of the Christian faith, who comprise about 16% of the population (Wilson, 1951:17).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972), religious architecture is not indicated as a type of large or impressive structures among the Nyakyusa. Rather, "the most impressive structure (or type of structure) in the community is the residence of a category of influential individuals, e.g., a noble, a wealthy landowner, or the local headman".

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "An element of the death ritual is the separation of corpse and spirit, the final disposal of the corpse, and the bringing of the new shade back 'to warm himself with the other shades' at the family hearth" (Wilson, 1957:204).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "They believe that the spirit (unsyuka) of a dead man survives underground (pasi) in the place of the shades (ubusyuka) and that it can and does visit surviving relatives in dreams and materially affect their destinies" (Wilson, 1957:17).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The place of the shades is a vague and shadowy land where no certain happiness is traditionally believed to be" (Wilson, 1957:17).

Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "They believe that the spirit (unsyuka) of a dead man survives underground (pasi) in the place of the shades (ubusyuka) and that it can and does visit surviving relatives in dreams and materially affect their destinies" (Wilson, 1957:17).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Some graves are oblong, some round or oval, according to lineage custom. In the round and oval graves the body is placed in the cave in a sitting position; in the oblong graves lying at full length on one arm; but in both the dead man is set to face the direction from which he and his people have traditionally come" (Wilson, 1957:15). Before burial, the body is washed, shaved, and wrapped in clothes (Wilson, 1957:16).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Some graves are oblong, some round or oval, according to lineage custom. In the round and oval graves the body is placed in the cave in a sitting position; in the oblong graves lying at full length on one arm; but in both the dead man is set to face the direction from which he and his people have traditionally come" (Wilson, 1957:15).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "Some graves are oblong, some round or oval, according to lineage custom. In the round and oval graves the body is placed in the cave in a sitting position..." (Wilson, 1957:15).

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Extended, lying on side

Notes: "Some graves are oblong, some round or oval, according to lineage custom....in the oblong graves [the body is placed] lying at full length on one arm..." (Wilson, 1957:15).

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850: Secondary Bone/Body Treatment (original scale), code=1, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "At all except the very poorest burials one or more head of cattle are killed. Cows are provided whenever possible, but, if no cows are available, bulls may be used instead" (Wilson, 1957:19).

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: No evidence for human co-sacrifices found in any ethnographic sources.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: "At all except the very poorest burials one or more head of cattle are killed. Cows are provided whenever possible, but, if no cows are available, bulls may be used instead" (Wilson, 1957:19).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "...they [kinsmen] put it [the body] in position in the cave together with a few personal possessions such as a pipe, an eating-pot, a little calabash of ointment, and one of beer; nowadays also a looking-glass and perhaps a pencil and a cup" (Wilson, 1957:16).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "...they [kinsmen] put it [the body] in position in the cave together with a few personal possessions such as a pipe, an eating-pot, a little calabash of ointment, and one of beer; nowadays also a looking-glass and perhaps a pencil and a cup" (Wilson, 1957:16).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "Whenever a death takes place, whether of man, woman, or child, a series of funeral rites lasting a month or more begins. The first of the series is the burial (ifwa) which, in the case of most adults, lasts three or four days, though for a rich man it may continue for a week, and for a child it is over in a day" (Wilson, 1957:13).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "The grave is dug in the swept and beaten earth that immediately surrounds the huts" (Wilson, 1957:15).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "...there is a lively belief in the survival of the dead and in the power of senior relatives, both living and dead, over their descendants..." (Wilson, 1957:3). "...the abasyuka, 'those who have risen from

the dead', that is, the shades" (Wilson, 1957:12).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Kyala may be seen as an important religious figure, but not a supreme high god. It is most likely that the Christian missionaries used the term Kyala to denote God when modifying Nyakyusa religion with Christian ideas. The minority group of Christians may believe in Kyala as a supreme high god, but it seems most probable that the majority of Nyakyusa does not subscribe to the belief in a supreme high god. "The phrase "their god" (Kyala gwabo) is normally used by pagans nowadays to mean the ancestral spirits, or some one among them. The term Kyala, which originally referred only to one of the most influential Nyakyusa spirits, has now been identified either with the Christian God or with divinity in general throughout all this area" (Wilson, 1939:37).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "...there is a lively belief in the survival of the dead and in the power of senior relatives, both living and dead, over their descendants..." (Wilson, 1957:3).

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "The shades, 'those who have risen from the dead', are the dead members of a lineage and, unless they were ruling chiefs when alive, they have power only over their own kinsmen, and are concerned only with behaviour between members of the lineage, not with behaviour towards outsiders" (Wilson, 1957:210).

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: Knowledge is not restricted, but power is. "The shades, 'those who have risen from the dead', are the dead members of a lineage and, unless they were ruling chiefs when alive, they have power only over their own kinsmen, and are concerned only with behaviour between members of the lineage, not with behaviour towards outsiders" (Wilson, 1957:210).

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: "But it is also thought that 'the shades see what is within a man': if he stints one wife of fish, then 'even though the woman herself has not said anything, the shades hear the thought of the belly'" (Wilson, 1957:218).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The kinsmen of the dead man gain prestige from a lavish funeral. They are compelled to sacrifice by fear lest the anger of the shades, or the 'breath' of their neighbours, should bring misfortune upon them, and they are rewarded by the admiration of men when they do so" (Wilson, 1957:32).

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: "There is much more talk among the Nyakyusa of misfortune from the shades or the anger of neighbours, than of blessing, but there is an idea, somewhat vague but real, that generosity and kindness will bring blessing (ulusajo)" (Wilson, 1957:220).

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "The mystical power of senior relatives (living and dead) can never be used irresponsibly—it cannot operate unless the cause is just—and therefore misfortune emanating from the shades is always a just retribution, not an irresponsible assault, like that made by witches" (Wilson, 1957:5).

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "The shades manifest themselves to the living in dreams or as snakes, and they come by night to the homestead to eat food set aside for them in the sacred grove or the senior wife's hut" (Wilson, 1957:211).

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Human spirits are within men

Notes: "But though the shades dwell beneath and visit the homesteads of their kinsmen seeking food and warmth, they are also within men—munda (in the belly)—they create desire, they control conception, and are ejected in intercourse as semen" (Wilson, 1957:212).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "They believe that the spirit (unsyuka) of a dead man survives underground (pasi) in the place of the shades (ubusyuka) and that it can and does visit surviving relatives in dreams and materially affect their destinies" (Wilson, 1957:17).

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "They believe that the spirit (unsyuka) of a dead man survives underground (pasi) in the place of the shades (ubusyuka) and that it can and

does visit surviving relatives in dreams and materially affect their destinies" (Wilson, 1957:17).

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: Shades will communicate with surviving relatives in dreams (Wilson, 1957:17).

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: Shades will communicate with surviving relatives in dreams (Wilson, 1957:17).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The heroic myths and genealogies proclaim the origin of chieftainship, and point to a distinction between ordinary chiefs and those we call 'divine kings'. Two remote ancestors who were pre-eminent are worshipped as heroes and creators, their graves are centres at which a large number of chiefdoms join in celebration, and living representatives are selected in every generation bearing their names. These are the 'divine kings', the Lwembe of Lubaga (in the centre of Nyakyusa country) and the Kyungu of Mbande near Karonga in Nyasaland. A third hero, Kyala, is associated with the cave, PaliKyala, near Ikombe at the north-east corner of the Lake, and he is worshipped in the same way as the other two, except that the priest of the cave is not his descendant and does not embody him" (Wilson, 1959:17).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "The link between religious beliefs and morality (in the sense of right behaviour) is very clear among the Nyakyusa. Many misfortunes are attributed to sin, that is, wrong-doings (inongwa) thought to be supernaturally punished" (Wilson, 1957:8).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: See Wilson, 1957:217

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: "...types of behaviour commonly believed to be directly punished by the shades [include]...turning on the seduction of a senior's wife by his junior..." (Wilson, 1957:216).

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Son seducing one of father's wives

Notes: "A son who has committed the most heinous offence of all, seducing one of his father's wives, can 'beg pardon' [to the shades] only by offering a cow" (Wilson, 1959:162).

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: See Wilson, 1957:216. Additionally, "...it is quarrelling between kinsmen that angers the shades and makes the celebration of certain rituals necessary..." (Wilson, 1959:164).

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: "Misfortune is also believed to come from the anger of senior relatives, living and dead. If a junior has angered his senior kinsman the senior is said to 'mutter over the fire'. 'He is so angry that he cannot speak intelligible words, he murmurs and mumbles to himself...' 'I crouch over the fire in the evening and mutter to myself in a low voice: "I am astonished and hurt at my son. Did I not provide marriage-cattle for him? And he does this to me!" Then the shades hear him and the wrong-doer falls ill, or is sterile, or his crops or fishing fail" (Wilson, 1957:179).

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: See Wilson, 1957:216

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: "The kinsmen of the dead man gain prestige from a lavish funeral. They are compelled to sacrifice by fear lest the anger of the shades, or the 'breath' of their neighbours, should bring misfortune upon them, and they are rewarded by the admiration of men when they do so" (Wilson, 1957:32).

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Favoritism

Notes: "Favouritism in a polygynous family, shown in the unfair division of milk or meat or fish by the husband between his wives, is thought to anger the shades, which cause his cows to

bleed from the udder when milked, or prevent fish entering his traps, and so do the bad temper and insulting language of a quarrelsome wife" (Wilson, 1957:217).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "Many misfortunes are attributed to sin, that is, wrong-doings (inongwa) thought to be supernaturally punished" (Wilson, 1957:8).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for specific information regarding the agents of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Shades of deceased humans are the agents of supernatural punishment (see Wilson, 1957, various pages such as 32, 218).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Shades of deceased humans are the agents of supernatural punishment (see Wilson, 1957, various pages such as 32, 218).

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: See Wilson, 1957, various pages including 214-215. "In the Nyakyusa view there is a direct and immediate link between misfortune and wrong-doing. When illness befalls a man, or his crops fail, or his cattle die, he reflects on any quarrels he may have had with kinsmen or affines or neighbours, and on any rituals he should have performed and has omitted wholly or in part" (Wilson, 1957:214).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The most salient reasons for supernatural punishment is to enforce religious ritual observances, as well as group norms. See questions below for specific information.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: For example: "The kinsmen of the dead man gain prestige from a lavish funeral. They are compelled to sacrifice by fear lest the anger of the shades, or the 'breath' of their neighbours, should bring misfortune upon them, and they are rewarded by the

admiration of men when they do so" (Wilson, 1957:32).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: See Wilson, 1957:217

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: "Only rarely is it suggested that punishment may be postponed until after death and then what is feared is that the shades of the lineage will not receive their kinsman" (Wilson, 1957:218).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: "Misfortune is also believed to come from the anger of senior relatives, living and dead. If a junior has angered his senior kinsman the senior is said to 'mutter over the fire'. Then the shades hear him and the wrong-doer falls ill, or is sterile, or his crops or fishing fail" (Wilson, 1957:179).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "Misfortune is also believed to come from the anger of senior relatives, living and dead. If a junior has angered his senior kinsman the senior is said to 'mutter over the fire'. Then the shades hear him and the wrong-doer falls ill, or is sterile, or his crops or fishing fail" (Wilson, 1957:179).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: "Misfortune is also believed to come from the anger of senior relatives, living and dead. If a junior has angered his senior kinsman the senior is said to 'mutter over the fire'. Then the shades hear him and the wrong-doer falls ill, or is sterile, or his crops or fishing fail" (Wilson, 1957:179).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: "Senior kinsmen, living and dead, have a mystical power over their juniors, but their anger is dangerous only if it is just. They cannot mutter irresponsibly. Kinsmen are

'members of one another' in the sense that the life and death of one affect the others. The sins of a father are visited on his children, his juniors in the lineage (though a woman's sins affect only her own husband and children), and the very fact of kinship makes a mystical bond between agnatic kin, descendants of a common great-grandfather, and a man and his daughters or sister's children" (Wilson, 1957:226).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Women can be punished in the form of harm done on their children. "All were agreed that a woman is in the power of the shades of her father's lineage and if her father is angry with her, or with his son-in-law her husband, his shades afflict her, causing her to be barren or to have miscarriages, or ailing children" (Wilson, 1957:181).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: "There is much more talk among the Nyakyusa of misfortune from the shades or the anger of neighbours, than of blessing, but there is an idea, somewhat vague but real, that generosity and kindness will bring blessing (ulusajo)" (Wilson, 1957:220).

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for details on the cause and purposes of supernatural rewards.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The shades of deceased human spirits may bring rewards (see Wilson, 1957:220).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The shades of deceased human spirits may bring rewards. "There is much more talk among the Nyakyusa of misfortune from the shades or the anger of neighbours, than of blessing, but there is an idea, somewhat vague but real, that generosity and kindness will bring blessing (ulusajo)" (Wilson, 1957:220).

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: see Wilson, 1957:220

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: "Of a man given a cow by the chief, it was sometimes said: 'The shades have blessed him; he has a righteous (ngolofu) shade'" (Wilson, 1957:220).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. As such, the society prescribes general social norms. "No linguistic distinction is made between an offence punished by the courts and one thought to be punished by the shades; both are wrong-doings (inongwa), and there is no sharp distinction between an offence against a living kinsman and an offence against a dead one. In short, there is no clear conception of 'sin' as opposed to 'tort' or 'crime'" (Wilson, 1957:215).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. Because of this, norms and morals of the Nyakyusa must be examined at the societal level. "Here we are concerned with the form of morality sanctioned by Nyakyusa religion, with the conception of good and evil, and with the relation between belief and behaviour" (Wilson, 1957:8).

What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: "In Nyakyusa society the distinction is fairly clear-cut: ubunyago, which is translated here as a ritual, means a series of actions directed towards the shades or heroes, and enforced by mystical sanctions, as opposed to action which is merely customary and conventional (ulwiho)" (Wilson, 1957:9).

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Law is holy in the sense that right behaviour (or morality) is always linked to religion" (Wilson, 1957:228). See Wilson, 1957:8-9, and questions below for more detail

Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: See Wilson 1957:215

Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

Notes: "The moral law is thought to operate also within the age-village, where the just are protected and the evil punished by 'the breath of men'; but within both lineage

and village irresponsible and malicious injury by witches or sorcerers is possible" (Wilson, 1957:226).

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only one class of society

Notes: "...moral obligations are limited to kinsmen and neighbours: they do not extend beyond the chiefdom except to those relatives who may live beyond its bounds" (Wilson, 1959:201).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. Because of this, virtues are not exclusive to religion, but reflect the centrally important values advocated by the Nyakyusa society. See below for specific virtues. For a discussion on Nyakyusa values, see Wilson, 1951, Chapter IV: Values.

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: "The conception of impurity, uncleanness, associated with physiological functions of coition, excretion, menstruation, childbirth and death is, as we have already suggested, a very widespread one. The Nyakyusa perhaps emphasize it more than their neighbours (though not more than the Jews or the Hindus), and their preoccupation with purification in the rituals is paralleled by the emphasis laid on cleanliness (ubwifyusi) in person, in house and courtyard, in cooking, and in disposal of excrement" (Wilson, 1957:207).

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: "The all-embracing virtue to the Nyakyusa is wisdom (amahala). It includes the enjoyment of company and the practice of hospitality, for no man is wise who is surly, or aloof, or stingy; it includes neighbourly behaviour, dignity, and respect for law and convention, but it does not include display. The wise may dance, but they do not need to dance in order to be wise, and those who commit adultery, or are boastful, or quarrelsome show foolishness (ubukonyofu) and sinful pride (amatingo), the opposite of wisdom. Wisdom is expressed in all relationships, not only in village relationships, but it is learned in the village; pagan Nyakyusa insist that 'it is by conversing with our friends that we gain wisdom'" (Wilson, 1951:89).

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: "The conception of impurity, uncleanness, associated with physiological functions of coition, excretion, menstruation, childbirth and death is, as we have already suggested, a very widespread one. The Nyakyusa perhaps emphasize it more than their neighbours (though not more than the Jews or the Hindus), and their preoccupation with purification in the rituals is paralleled by the emphasis laid on cleanliness (ubwifyusi) in person, in house and courtyard, in cooking, and in disposal of excrement" (Wilson, 1957:207).

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Hospitality

Notes: See Wilson, 1951:15

– Yes [specify]: Friendship

Notes: "One of the values most constantly stressed by the Nyakyusa is that of ukwangala which, in its primary sense, means 'the enjoyment of good company' and, by extension, the mutual aid and sympathy which spring from personal friendship" (Wilson, 1951:66).

– Yes [specify]: Dignity

Notes: "Though the Nyakyusa lay so much stress on geniality, and praise a man for being 'a good mixer', yet they greatly admire dignity (ubusisya). To be nsisya (dignified, impressive) is one of the attributes of chiefs and village headmen, sought, as we have seen, through medicines; but ordinary men may also aspire to it in their persons and homesteads. Indeed, ubusisya bwa nkaja, the dignity of the homestead, is one of the legitimate channels of ambition to a Nyakyusa, and is something achieved largely through hard work" (Wilson, 1951:77).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. As a society, the Nyakyusa highly emphasize sexual morality; this value is reflected in ritual, magical, and legal practices of society. Infractions on sexual taboos may even result in death (see section on Enforcement below). (see Wilson, 1951, Chapter IV: Values, Section D: Decency).

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: "The basis of Nyakyusa sexual morality is the separation of the sexual activities of successive generations, more particularly the separation of the sexual activities of mothers and sons, and the complete segregation of fathers-in-law and daughters-in-law" (Wilson, 1951:82).

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: "The basis of Nyakyusa sexual morality is the separation of the sexual activities of successive generations, more particularly the separation of the sexual activities of mothers and sons, and the complete segregation of fathers-in-law and daughters-in-law" (Wilson, 1951:82).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "...the only occasions of prayer to the shades [of the deceased] are when men are in trouble and anticipate misfortune" (Wilson, 1957:214).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "The religion of the Nyakyusa is expressed in ritual rather than in dogma. Everyone participates, at some time or another, in a variety of rituals; a great deal of time and energy is devoted to them, and they are elaborate" (Wilson, 1957:6). "We [the author] proceed on the assumption that man express in ritual what moves them most; that the form of expression is conventional and obligatory, and that therefore in ritual the values of a group (as opposed to those of individuals) are revealed" (Wilson, 1957:8).

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "...the meticulous performance of the rituals is stressed: the right medicines; the right persons; the right order of events are all important. The attitude of mind of the participants matters also—if they are on bad terms the ritual will be ineffective—but goodwill and forgiveness alone are useless without the performance of the proper ritual" (Wilson, 1959:202).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: The Nyakyusa have two levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). "Traditionally villages were grouped in a number of small independent chiefdoms led by hereditary chiefs. Each chiefdom contained many kinsmen, but there was no fiction of common descent of all the men of a chiefdom, or of chiefs and people. There were thus three types of social group: villages occupied by age-mates, who shared common land rights, and herded and fought together; lineages bound by common interest in inherited cattle and common rituals; and chiefdoms in which the bond was occupation of a common territory and allegiance to a common chief" (Wilson, 1957:2).

Education

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The British Administration has established two schools, one under the Administration and one under the Native Authority. The British established the centralized Native Authority in 1926, which groups the traditionally sovereign chiefs of the Nyakyusa into 11 court districts with "one chief as president of the Native Court in each; these eleven chiefs, together with the two presidents of the Ndali and Lambya courts, belong to a single federation, with an appeal court and joint Native treasury of its own" (Wilson, 1951:16).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that there is no food storage present among the Nyakyusa (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 232 (agricultural intensity) indicates that irrigation is not present among the Nyakyusa (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14 indicates that routes of land transport are unimproved trails, and therefore, transportation infrastructure is presumably not present (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. "Law is a condition of social survival; no society can exist without it; and in so far as religion helps to maintain law and order it fulfills a necessary social function. Among the Nyakyusa (and perhaps in all societies) order is maintained partly by fear of supernatural sanctions. The rituals we have described both enhance fear and relieve it. They harness fear to social ends" (Wilson, 1957:232). Additionally, SCCS variable 90, indicates that police are not specialized (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. Judges are not institutionalized among the Nyakyusa, but a clear process exists to maintain order. "The Nyakyusa set great store on arbitration by a friend. It is common

practice for individuals who have quarrelled to state their dispute before a respected friend and ask for his opinion on the case. The statement is made in public and any man who happens to be present may offer an opinion. The respected friend to whom the case is first submitted is most often the leader of the village-section to which one or both parties to the dispute belong. But he need not necessarily be an appointed leader; any respected man may be asked to arbitrate. If his decision is not accepted by both parties, or if he declares the case too difficult and refuses to give an opinion, then it is taken to the headman of the village. Should the headman fail to settle the dispute, it goes to the senior headman of his side of the chiefdom, thence to the chief sitting with his headmen, and nowadays it may go on through the Native Court, and the Native Appeal Court, to the District Officer sitting with native assessors, the Provincial Commissioner, and the High Court of Tanganyika." (Wilson, 1951:136).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The [British] Administration has not attempted to suppress arbitration among the Nyakyusa, though the villagers say they have been told to 'bring all cases to Court and write them in the book'" (Wilson, 1951:139).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. As a society, the Nyakyusa do not have a formal legal code, but rather a traditional law relating to theft, adultery, murder, and witchcraft. Lineages and villages are responsible for the behavior of its individuals, and take charge of upholding their members to the traditional laws. Infractions were dealt with in a generally standardized manner among all villages. (Wilson, 1957:2). See questions below for more details on punishment.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: "An adulterer or cattle-thief was speared by the injured party and his kinsmen, if they could catch him. If they could not, they might attack any member of his age-village" (Wilson, 1957:2).

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: "...witchcraft was treated as an offence against the state, and the property of a convicted witch went to the chief" (Wilson, 1957:2).

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Nyakyusa have access to, and are subject to the British Administration's Courts. Punishment is most typically in the form of a fine (Wilson, 1951:139).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. As a society, the Nyakyusa do not have a formal legal code, but rather a traditional law relating to theft, adultery, murder, and witchcraft. Lineages and villages are responsible for the behavior of its individuals, and take charge of upholding their members to the traditional laws. (see Wilson, 1957:2).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. As a society, the Nyakyusa provide food for themselves. Their primary mode of subsistence is intensive agriculture utilizing green manuring, rotation of crops, periodic fallows, and tools such as hoes (Wilson, 1951:6-8). Animal husbandry provides a secondary source of subsistence, and hunting and fishing provide additional supplemental sources of food. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Nyakyusa political and religious realms of life are intertwined to the extent that they are best considered coterminous. As a society, the Nyakyusa provide food for themselves. Their primary mode of subsistence is intensive agriculture utilizing green manuring, rotation of crops, periodic fallows, and tools such as hoes (Wilson, 1951:6-8). Animal husbandry provides a secondary source of subsistence, and hunting and fishing provide additional supplemental sources of food. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.